

REFORMS IN THE CULTURE AND ART SECTOR AS A NEW STAGE OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

Djalilov Bakhtiyor Khidayevich

Candidate of Philosophical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department
“Fundamentals of Philosophy and Spirituality” of the Mirzo Ulugbek National
University of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15489915>

Annotation: This article examines the changes implemented since Uzbekistan’s independence with the goal of advancing the country’s cultural and artistic industries. It looks at how long-standing traditions and customs are maintained, passed down to future generations, and how young people are raised with a sense of patriotism while developing their aesthetic sensibilities. The article also examines the normative-legal documents, such as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan’s decrees and resolutions, that have been adopted to support creative teams and fortify the material and technical foundation of cultural institutions.

Key words: tradition, culture, development, education, society, cultural heritage, spirituality, communication, technology.

Since the day our country gained independence, attention has been paid to various fields, including culture and arts. The spiritual life of our people, the centuries-old traditions and customs of the Uzbeks, their festivals and ceremonies, and the intangible cultural heritage passed down orally have been restored, with significant efforts made to preserve and transmit them to future generations. In our country’s cultural system, one of the main tasks has been defined as nurturing young students and children in a national spirit, shaping their aesthetic consciousness, and fostering a sense of patriotism. In this regard, the provision of material and technical support to cultural institutions and creative teams is noteworthy.

It is well known from the historical development path of any country that its rapid progress, achievement of specific successes, and the well-being of its people depend on the level of attention given to the education and upbringing of youth and their future. In this regard, the efforts made in the fields of education and upbringing in our country demonstrate the high level of attention paid to young people [1].

Indeed, our country has created broad opportunities for young people to receive education and upbringing and to deeply study the fields they desire and are interested in. After all, one of the most important tasks today is to nurture well-rounded, ambitious, and energetic youth who possess modern knowledge

and skills and who can take responsibility for the worthy future of the country. In nurturing such accomplished youth, the role of culture and art is invaluable. Cultural institutions also play a significant role in this process. These opportunities are reflected in a number of decrees and resolutions issued by our President. Among them are the Decree No. RP-3920 dated August 26, 2018, of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures for the innovative development of the culture and art sector” [2], Decree No. RP-4038 dated November 28, 2018, “On approval of the concept for the further development of national culture in the republic of Uzbekistan” [3], the Decree No. DP-6000 dated May 26, 2020, “On measures to further enhance the role and importance of the sphere of culture and art in the life of society” [4], and Decree No. RP-112 dated February 2, 2022, “On additional measures for the further development of the culture and art sector” [5], all of which have initiated a new stage of reforms in this field.

Specifically, the main objectives of the Concept for the Further Development of National Culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan have been defined as follows:

- to improve the normative-legal framework related to the field of culture, the institutional system in this sector, and the activities of cultural institutions;
- to preserve our historical and cultural heritage and widely apply it in the education of the younger generation;
- to instill national and universal values in the minds of our youth, to preserve and nurture ethnic cultural traditions, and on this basis, to support folk creativity;
- to create and expand necessary conditions for the realization of the creative potential of the population, including young people;
- to widely introduce modern information and communication technologies into the cultural sphere, and to effectively use innovative ideas and technologies in the broader research and promotion of culture;
- to ensure the active participation of citizens, including persons with disabilities, in cultural life and their social equality in accessing cultural services;
- to establish and develop mutually effective international relations in the cultural sphere, to view national culture as an integral part of world culture, and to pay special attention to equality and respect for human rights in this regard;
- to ensure that economic, social, and cultural policy decisions align with the unified state policy in this sector;

➤ to guarantee the full functioning of cultural and art institutions, to further strengthen their material resource base, and to implement public oversight in the preservation and protection of cultural sites [3].

It is clear from the aforementioned analysis that Uzbekistan has given particular attention to the advancement of the arts and culture since gaining independence. In order to preserve our people's rich historical and cultural legacy for future generations, important reforms have been implemented and centuries-old traditions and customs have been brought back to life. One of the cultural system's top priorities in our nation has been determined to be fostering the sense of patriotism and national pride in the younger generation.

At the same time, steps have been planned to support creative teams, enhance the activities of cultural and artistic institutions, and fortify their technical and material foundation. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan's decrees and decisions have established a significant legal basis. The idea of developing national culture specifically entails a number of duties, including fostering the creative potential of young people, protecting historical and cultural heritage, and guaranteeing that citizens actively participate in cultural life.

The growth of the culture and arts sector is crucial for the spiritual development of the younger generation, forming their aesthetic preferences, and fostering in them a spirit of high human values, in addition to maintaining and transmitting the nation's identity to future generations. As a result, ongoing reforms will be implemented in the future to further develop this sector in our nation.

References:

1. Humoyunmirzo Zahriddinbobir O'G'Li Umarov (2024). THE NEED FOR ORGANIZING YOUTH LEISURE TIME IN CULTURAL CENTERS. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 5(1), 455-460.
2. Presidential Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. RP-3920 dated August 26, 2018, "On Measures for the Innovative Development of the Culture and Art Sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan" // <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-3882752>
3. Presidential Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. RP-4038 dated November 28, 2018, "On Approval of the Concept for Further Development of National Culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan" // <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-4084926#-4085930>

4. Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-6000 dated May 26, 2020, "On Measures to Further Increase the Role and Influence of Culture and Art in Society" // <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-4829149>
5. Presidential Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. RP-112 dated February 2, 2022, "On Additional Measures for the Further Development of the Culture and Art Sector" // <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-5849580#-5849669>
6. Sobirovich, T. B. (2021). Philosophical Dialectics of National and Universal Cultural Development. Irish Interdisciplinary Journal of Science & Research (IJSR).
7. Sobirovich, T. B. (2020). The development of democratic society and spiritual renewal in the views of Eastern and Western thinkers. International journal of advanced research and review, 5(10), 60-65.
8. Sobirovich, T. B. (2024). The Dynamics of Ancient Thought: How Philosophies Shaped Changing Societal Ideospheres. Dynamics, 8(3), 19-24.

